

Pool of Siloam

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Entry tags: Pool, Archaeological Site, Ancient Western Asia, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Ancient Mediterranean, Early Christianity, Greek, Language, Southern Levant, Jerusalem, Religious Place, Southern Levant, Jewish Traditions, Judeans and Israelites, Judaism

The Pool of Siloam was constructed in the mid-first century BCE and remained in use until the city was destroyed by the Roman army during the First Revolt in 70 CE. This pool was constructed at the base of the city's Eastern Ridge whose southernmost rock outcropping can be seen hanging above the pool. It sat in Jerusalem's Central Valley, near its convergence with the city's other two large valleys, the Kidron and Hinnom. This natural catchment basin would receive water flow during the rainy season and refill the pool. However, the main source of water was the nearby Siloam Tunnel. A rock-cut channel from the tunnel's outlet which directed spring water into the Siloam Pool. Archaeological work has progressively uncovered pieces of the Pool of Siloam since the 1890s, and it continues to be excavated today. Although only three sides of the pool are known, it seems to have been four sided and included a portico on at least its northwestern side. The pool consisted of a series of steps that led people into the water below. The steps were built in increments of four with a wide step in between. To date, three staircases are known, and the depth of the bottom of the pool has not yet been determined. After the destruction of Jerusalem in 70 CE, many of the large stone slabs from the pool were robbed out and used as building stone elsewhere in the city. Some remains of the pool were preserved due to water erosion which covered the pool with thick deposits. This area was later developed as a garden and became known in Arabic as Birket al-Hamra ("The Red Pool"). Many scholars believe the pool was used for ritual immersion by the Jewish community in Jerusalem and those who arrived in the city for the pilgrimage festivals. The Temple Mount is located north of the Siloam Pool and could be accessed by a road that traversed the Central Valley in a north-south manner. Ritually purified worshipers could ascend the sacred mountain from below and approach the temple to participate in the sacrificial cult. The Pool of Siloam undoubtedly attracted crowds of people and carried a social function as well. The pool is mentioned in ancient literary sources. The New Testament Gospel of John describes a miraculous healing where Jesus placed mud on a blind man's eyes and instructed him to go wash in the pool (John 9). Upon washing the mud from his eyes, the man's sight was restored. The Mishnah describes a libation that was taken from the pool and poured into a basin at the temple altar during the festival of Sukkot (M. Sukkah 4).

Date Range: 80 BCE - 70 CE

Region: Pool of Siloam

Region tags: Israel, Jerusalem

A stepped pool used for immersion on the southern part of ancient Jerusalem.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Excavating the City of David Where Jerusalem's History Began by Ronny Reich

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://www.sefaria.org/Mishnah_Sukkah.4?lang=bi

– Source 1 Description: Mishnah Sukkah 4

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=John%209&version=NIV>

– Source 2 Description: John 9

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2004

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Ronny Reich and Eli Shukron

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Pre-modern

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1894-1897

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Fredrick Jones Bliss and Archibald Dickie

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Although portions of the northeastern end of the pool have been excavated in a scientific manner, a large amount of dirt was removed by heavy machinery without normative excavation methods.

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2022-present

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Israel Antiquities Authority

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

– Other [specify]: Valley

Notes: The Pool of Siloam sits at the outlet of the Siloam Tunnel and in the bottom of Jerusalem's Central Valley, at the point where it converges with the Kidron and Hinnon Valleys.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Water feature

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

Notes: The pool itself was built as a single structure.

One single feature

–Other [specify]: This structure had multiple features.

A group of structures:

– No

A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: The multiple features of the pool include: the pool itself, the nearby Siloam Tunnel which discharged spring water into the pool, a portico which covered at least part of the pool, and a large southern dam wall.

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The pool itself seems to have been built in two phases. The first phase was a pool built of plaster steps. It was later rebuilt with large well-cut limestone paving stones. Scholars believe that the Early Roman Period Pool of Siloam was preceded by a pool that was built in the Iron Age II, although no evidence of the earlier pool as been found. The Pool of Siloam sits at the outlet of the Siloam Tunnel which was hewn out in the Iron Age II (late 8th century BCE or early 7th century BCE). This water was harnessed to fill the pool by a rock-cut channel.

Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: Purification

Notes: While many scholars believe the pool was used for ritual purification, similar to a mikveh (Jewish ritual bath), it undoubtedly had a social function as well.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: An area to the west of the Pool of Siloam was later converted into a Byzantine Church remembering Jesus' healing of a blind man (John 9).

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: The pool's large limestone slabs seem to have been robbed out and used as building stone after Jerusalem was destroyed by the Roman army in 70 CE.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Water erosion covered the portions of the pool that remained until they began to be recovered by archaeologists in the late 19th century CE.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Although the Pool of Siloam was not directly used in Jewish worship, its water did seem to have a ritual purification function.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: In its initial phase, the pool seems to have been constructed by the Hasmonean Kings and was later paved with large stone slabs by Roman rulers, perhaps Herod the Great.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Other [specify]: The initial building of the Pool of Siloam in the Early Roman Period may have simply been a pragmatic renovation of an earlier pool that sat on the same spot. It may also have had religious motivations, but that is not clear.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

- No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

- Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

- I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

- I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

- I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

- I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

- I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Plaster

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: A portico with columns was present on at least the northwestern side of the pool.

↳ On the inside:

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– No

Notes: Although floral motifs are very common in Jewish communities of the Early Roman Period in Jerusalem, none have yet been found at the Pool of Siloam.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

Notes: Although traces of paint are not detectible presently, at least parts of the pool may have been painted in antiquity.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Notes: Mosaics are common in Jewish communities during the Early Roman Period, but none have yet been found at the Pool of Siloam.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Notes: It is possible that further excavations will bring more decorations to light in the future.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The Mishnah (Sukkah 4.9-10) describes a libation ritual that would take place during the festival of Sukkot in which water from the Pool of Siloam was poured into a basin at the temple altar.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Annually

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The Mishnah (Sukkot 4.9-10) relates that there were two basins at the temple altar, one of which received wine libations and the other, water. It also describes an instance where a Sadducean priest intentionally poured water on his feet rather than into the correct basin, angering the people watching.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: Jews wishing to participate in sacrifice and worship at the temple would need to be ritually purified through immersion in water fit for the purpose. The Pool of Siloam seems to have been used for ritual immersion, but there were other ritual baths in Jerusalem that could be used for this purpose as well. Therefore, it was not mandatory.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Notes: Although regular maintenance of the Pool of Siloam must have been performed, we have no details about what this process looked like and if it involved ritual activities.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– obligatory for some

Notes: The Torah specifies that all Israelite men are required to journey to the location of the tabernacle (later the temple in Jerusalem) during three festivals: Matzoth (Unleavened Bread), Shavu'ot (Pentecost), and Sukkot (Booths). Scholars debate the time when this became a requirement, as well as the degree to which it was practiced. However, there is evidence for connections between the Jewish Galilee and Jerusalem in the first centuries BCE and CE.

Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Field doesn't know

Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: The Torah specifies that all Israelite men are required to journey to the location of the tabernacle (later the temple in Jerusalem) during three festivals: Matzoth (Unleavened Bread), Shavu'ot (Pentecost), and Sukkot (Booths). Scholars debate the time when this became a requirement, as well as the degree to which it was practiced. However, there is evidence for connections between the Jewish Galilee and Jerusalem in the first centuries BCE and CE.

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Annual

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Notes: The Torah specifies that all Israelite males were to attend the festival, but nothing prohibited women from doing so.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Unknown

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– Yes

Notes: Many scholars assume the pool was used for ritual immersion.

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: A story of miraculous healing in the gospel of John chapter 9 describes Jesus placing mud over the eyes of a blind man and instructing him to go and wash at the Pool of Siloam. Upon washing, the man was able to see. The story is notable, even if there is no other ancient evidence that the pool was used in healing practices.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Due to the pool's large size and ritual use in the temple, this must have been the case. However, the available data does not allow us to be more specific about the pool's maintenance.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The pool seems to have been publicly accessible. In addition to its function as a large ritual bath, it undoubtedly also served a social function.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Pool of Siloam, Reich, Ronny. *Excavating the City of David Where Jerusalem's History Began*. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society, 2011. p.225-237

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